

FELLOWSHIP

MAY 2026

Kottayam's City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories,
concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

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Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance, and cultural context of their cities. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and developing thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is an emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

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Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Acknowledgment

This document began not on paper, but in conversations, quiet, everyday ones that gradually revealed the many ways people experience and remember the city. It took shape across tea stalls, homes, streets, and workplaces, through the hopes, frustrations, and quiet observations of Kottayam's residents, where affection for the city and its challenges exist side by side.

Through this process of listening and observing, I was able to see my own city through a new lens. What emerged was not just an understanding of urban systems, but a deeper awareness of how closely a city is held together by memory, routine, and care.

I would like to sincerely thank the Nāgrika team for providing the platform, guidance, and consistent support that made this City Vision Document possible. The resources shared throughout the process, the workshops, and the detailed feedback on the work were invaluable in shaping both the content and approach of this document. The two cohort meetings with fellow participants were especially enriching, offering the opportunity to engage with diverse perspectives on cities beyond Kottayam, and helping deepen my understanding of urban life more broadly. This collective learning process played an important role in strengthening how I see and interpret my own city today.

I am deeply grateful to all the interviewees who generously shared their time, experiences, and perspectives. Their voices form the foundation of this work and give it its depth and direction.

Why this Vision Document?

This document begins with a simple but important question: who gets to tell the story of a city?

Too often, cities are described through plans, reports, and proposals that look at them from a distance. But a city is not only built through infrastructure, it is lived through routine, memory, frustration, and hope. The people who wake up here, move through its streets, adapt to its changes, and carry its identity are not just participants in the city, they are its most informed observers.

This City Vision Document is built on that understanding. It brings together voices of residents across Kottayam: students, workers, teachers, officials, and families, who experience the city not as an abstract idea, but as a part of their everyday lives. They have witnessed its transitions, from quieter neighbourhoods to busier roads, from open grounds to built spaces, from familiarity to change. They understand not only what the city is, but what it is becoming.

Kottayam already holds a strong collective identity. It is a city shaped by literacy, conversation, and awareness, a place where people read, question, discuss, and form opinions. This culture of engagement extends beyond institutions into everyday life, into tea shops, homes, and public spaces. There is also a shared sense of familiarity and recognition, where people know each other, look out for one another, and remain connected through overlapping social worlds.

This document is an expression of that collective identity. It does not attempt to define the city from the outside, but to reflect what already exists within it.

At the same time, it creates space to name what often remains unspoken. Concerns around traffic, waste management, loss of public spaces, environmental degradation, and unplanned growth emerge not as isolated complaints, but as shared patterns across conversations. Alongside these concerns are clear and grounded aspirations, for better planning, more opportunities for youth, preservation of natural systems, and a city that grows without losing what makes it meaningful.

This document is not a final answer. It is an invitation.

An invitation for citizens to recognise their shared experiences, for policymakers to listen more closely, and for both to participate in shaping what comes next. It is rooted in the belief that the future of Kottayam does not lie only in plans or projects, but in the collective imagination and agency of the people who call it home.

Meet Kottayam

At six in the morning, the city is already awake, moving quietly before the day gathers pace.

At a tea stall by the roadside, a man folds open his newspaper with care, smoothing its creases before taking the first sip of his tea. A bus slows down, not quite stopping, as a few passengers step off with practiced ease. Somewhere in the distance, church bells begin to ring. A few seconds later, temple chimes follow. By the time the azan carries through the air, the city has settled into its morning rhythm. This pace carries through the rest of the day, shaping how the city moves and how people experience it.

Streets gradually come alive with school-going children and small businesses opening, but the movement remains steady, not urgent. Activity spreads itself across the day, moving through institutions, markets, and neighbourhood centres in a dispersed rhythm. At the same time, just beyond the busier streets, a different rhythm unfolds. Away from the movement of shops and schools, boatmen move slowly through the backwaters, tracing familiar routes as they ferry people and goods, while fishermen cast their nets in practiced, unhurried motions. In the low-lying paddy fields, work begins early, figures bent over in the distance, moving steadily through the land, in sync with the season and the soil. These contrasting yet connected rhythms, of the town and its edges, of street and water and field exist side by side, shaping how Kottayam lives and moves.

By evening, the city shifts into something more social. Tea shops and roadside stalls fill up. People of all ages pause, for tea, for *pazhampori*, for conversation. Some drift towards the few cafés that have emerged in recent years. Others return to verandas, to familiar corners, to *Thirunakkara Maidanam*, or to the river banks when the heat begins to lift. For those who can, the day stretches a little further, to the backwaters of *Kumarakom*.

This is a city where routine is not just functional, it is deeply social. It lives in the way people begin their day with the newspaper, not just to read but to discuss, in the ease with which conversations turn into debates at tea stalls, in how people recognize each other on the street, and in how lives quietly overlap. Here, paying attention to one another, sometimes as care, sometimes as curiosity is part of everyday life. It is this constant engagement that gives Kottayam its character, and makes its identity as ‘*Aksharanagari*’ or ‘City of Letters’ feel real.

INTRODUCTION

This identity did not emerge suddenly. It has been shaped over time, through a long-standing culture of reading, writing, and public discussion. Kottayam was one of the earliest centres of printing and publishing in Kerala, where newspapers like Malayala Manorama and Deepika took root, and institutions like CMS College helped build a strong foundation for education and intellectual exchange. Publishers such as DC Books further strengthened this culture, making literature widely accessible and embedding reading deeply into everyday life.

But these were not just institutions, they created an ecosystem. Printing presses, publishing houses, libraries, and educational institutions together shaped a city where language, ideas, and conversation became part of daily life. Generations grew up not just with access to education, but with an expectation to read, to question, and to engage.

And across conversations, this identity surfaced again and again, people spoke of Kottayam as ‘*Aksharanagari*’ with pride, and of themselves as Kottayamkar, with a quiet sense of belonging.

This sense of belonging is not limited to intellectual life, it extends into how communities live together and share space. Churches, temples, and mosques exist in proximity, their sounds and rhythms marking time across the day. Festivals like Onam, Vishu, Christmas and Eid bring people together, but it is the smaller, everyday interactions that sustain this sense of belonging.

Life here unfolds through informal spaces at tea shops, markets, religious compounds, and waterfront edges, where familiarity shapes interaction, and the city feels closely held. This closeness, built through everyday encounters and shared routines, is what gives Kottayam its continuity.

And this continuity is not only social, but it is also deeply rooted in the landscape the city is embedded within. Kottayam sits within a shifting terrain, at the heart of Kerala, between the backwaters of Kumarakom and the rising slopes of the Western Ghats. To the west lie the Vembanad Lake and the Kuttanad wetlands, where land and water are in constant negotiation, shaping cultivation, livelihoods, and settlement. To the east, the land gradually lifts into cooler, forested highlands, creating a transition that is both ecological and experiential within a short distance. These edges are not distant, they shape everyday life in the city itself, influencing climate, movement, food, and the rhythms people live by.

INTRODUCTION

Between these edges lies the midland terrain where the city rests, undulating, green, and layered with rubber plantations, coconut groves, and homestead gardens. Rivers like the Meenachil and Manimala move through this landscape, linking hills to backwaters, shaping how people settle and move. Water availability, soil conditions, and seasonal flows influence everything from where homes are built and their architecture to how people travel and work. This is not a static geography, but one that changes with the seasons, especially under the force of the monsoon.

During the monsoon, this relationship intensifies. Water rises, soil softens, and the landscape shifts, quietly but perceptibly. The backwaters swell, the paddy fields of Kuttanad respond to cycles of flooding and cultivation, and daily life adjusts to the presence of water, from altered routes of movement to changes in work and routine. For many, this is not disruption but rhythm, one that has long defined how people live and work with the land.

By contrast, summers bring a different experience of the same landscape. The heat settles in, shaped by both the inland terrain and the nearby water bodies, slowing the day, while homestead gardens come into season, mangoes, jackfruit, and other local fruits becoming part of everyday life. Even within the city, these cycles are felt, in shade, in food, in the pace of the day.

Kottayam is not defined by a single geography. It is a continuum of water, slope, and season, within which its rhythms, relationships, and ways of life come together. If you arrive in Kottayam, do not look for it in its landmarks alone. The city may not always move slowly, but to truly meet it, you have to slow down. In the pause over a cup of tea, in conversations that linger, in the quiet movement of water and people, and in the ways lives remain closely held. It is in these small, continuous moments that the city reveals itself.

State	Kerala
District	Kottayam
Population	Approx. 2.2 lakh (municipal area)
Area	Approx. 22.87 sq. km
Type of City Government	Municipal council
Languages prevalent	Malayalam (primary), English widely used

INTRODUCTION

Growing up in Kottayam, near the Meenachil River, I witnessed the city changing with the seasons, its quiet life revolving around water. I was born and schooled here, and even after leaving for college, I found myself returning almost every weekend. It was never just where I was from, but where my life continued to unfold. Summers brought stillness and the beginning of mango season, with afternoons spent plucking fruits from the backyard, while weekends often led to the backwaters of Kumarakom. Whenever I needed a pause, the hills of Vagamon and Idukki were always close enough, offering a quiet shift in landscape and climate.

Then came the monsoons, changing everything. I remember quietly watching the first drops of rain, the way the smell of the earth would shift from soft and sharp at first, then deeper and heavier as the rains grew stronger. The sound of rain became constant, settling into the rhythm of daily life, blurring time and slowing everything down. Coming back now feels both familiar and different. The same warmth in people, in conversations, in the way life unfolds without urgency. There is a quiet continuity in everyday life, even as small shifts become noticeable over time. For me, Kottayam has always been a place shaped by water, landscape, and community, and now, when I view the city, it feels like a changing place that still holds my heart.

This City Vision Document draws on 29 in-depth interviews conducted across Kottayam between 01 February 2026 and 15 March 2026. The conversations span a wide cross-section of the city's residents and stakeholders: senior citizens who remember the city before its current congestion; the youth of Kottayam navigating what it means to stay or leave; elected councillors and the Municipal Chairperson working within the constraints of governance; school teachers observing shifts in how children experience the city; Kathakali artists, social workers, and civil society leaders who engage with the city's cultural and civic life daily.

The interviews were conducted as open conversations rather than structured surveys. Questions moved from daily routine to memory to frustration to vision. Citizens were asked where they spend their time, what places mean to them, what has changed, what worries them, and what they hope for. What emerged from these conversations is not a simple list of complaints, but a layered portrait of a city in a particular moment, aware of its richness, anxious about its direction, and capable of articulating both with precision and care.

Four themes organise what the interviews collectively reveal: Everyday Life, which examines how citizens experience the city on an ordinary day; Places of Belonging, which documents the spaces that carry identity and memory; Voices of Concern, which surfaces the structural problems that citizens identify most urgently; and Dreams for Tomorrow, which maps what citizens want Kottayam to become. Together, these themes move from lived experience toward policy possibility, from what the city is toward what it could be.

Meet the Citizens

To understand Kottayam, it is not enough to observe the city, you have to understand the lives that move through it. Across 29 conversations with residents of different categories: senior citizens, youth, teachers, councillors, active citizens, and others, a shared picture begins to emerge, not of a single way of living, but of overlapping routines, concerns, and relationships that shape the city from within.

The people interviewed are not just residents, but a deeply aware and engaged citizen base who experience the city with attention, memory, and emotional investment. Senior citizens act as memory keepers, grounding Kottayam in stories of what it once was, of open grounds, closer neighbourhoods, and a slower, more connected way of life. Youth reflects a strong sense of belonging paired with the reality of leaving in search of opportunity, holding on to a familiarity they do not easily find elsewhere. Teachers and active citizens articulate the city's identity and concerns with clarity, while councillors offer insight into both the possibilities and constraints of shaping the city through governance.

This process began with familiar conversations. I started by speaking to people I already knew, family members, friends, and neighbours. But even within these familiar circles, the conversations unfolded in unexpected ways. People I had known for years began to speak about Kottayam through memories, frustrations, and quiet observations that revealed a different side of both them and the city.

As the interviews expanded, so did my understanding. Across conversations, a shared pattern became visible, people are observant, informed, and closely connected to their surroundings. They recognise faces in everyday spaces, engage in casual yet meaningful conversations, and remain aware of the city's changes. Their concerns: traffic, environmental degradation, loss of public spaces, and unplanned growth are not distant complaints, but personal frustrations, often felt strongly but not always collectively voiced.

Some conversations led me to parts of the city I had overlooked. A Kathakali artist spoke about a quiet place nearby that I had never noticed before. Others pointed to everyday spaces: roadsides, riverbanks, small gathering points that do not appear on maps, but are deeply embedded in people's lives. Through these interactions, I began to see Kottayam not just as a place I was familiar with, but as one I had only partially understood.

What became clear through these 29 voices is that people care deeply about this city. Their engagement may be quiet, sometimes informal, but it is constant. It lives in observation, in conversation, in small acts of concern and belonging. Through this process, the city became more complex, but also more personal. What began as a documentation exercise turned into a process of rediscovery. Listening to these voices, familiar and unfamiliar, deepened my own relationship with Kottayam, revealing the layers of care, memory, and aspiration that exist within it. In many ways, this document is not just about the city. It is about the people who continue to shape it, question it, and believe in what it can become.

Glossary and Local Terms

Word or Phrase in Regional Language	Translation in English
<i>Pazhampori</i>	Banana Fritters
<i>Aksharanagari</i>	City of Letter
<i>Thattukadas</i>	Local eatery
<i>Chaya kadas</i>	Tea shop
<i>Kadi</i>	Snacks

Everyday Life

Everyday Life

Prologue

Most residents in Kottayam begin their day between 5:30 and 7:00 AM. Morning routines are shaped by faith—prayers, *kirthans*, visits to churches and temples, and by the school run, which for most families means a two-wheeler or car rather than a bus. The working day begins early, not out of urgency, but out of habit—people have learned to complete their essential travel before the town centre begins to slow under congestion. Afternoons are given to errands and family. By evening, the city turns social—temple grounds, cafés, and old restaurants begin to fill and by 9:30 PM, the streets are already emptying.

This is the rhythm of an ordinary day in Kottayam.

But to understand how this rhythm feels from within, it is not enough to begin in the present. Every city is also the city it used to be, and in Kottayam, that earlier version sits very close to the surface.

In conversations with those who have known the city the longest, another Kottayam begins to emerge. A senior citizen remembers evenings at Thirunakkara Maidanam when there was still space to sit, the YMCA where friends gathered over basketball and billiards, and a hotel at Central Junction where students lingered for hours over tea and conversation. An active citizen recalls football in church courtyards after school, swimming in the Meenachil, and walking into a neighbour's house unannounced. "There were no 'No Entry' signs at any house. You were welcome anywhere."

That version of the city has not disappeared entirely, but it has shifted. The river is no longer something people easily enter. Visiting a home now often begins with a phone call. What remains are fragments, memories that still shape how people measure the present.

These recollections do not simply evoke nostalgia; they offer a baseline, a way of understanding what everyday life in Kottayam once made possible, and how quietly it has changed. Today, the city carries approximately 1.25 lakh residents, while absorbing a floating population of over 3 lakh each day, a city doing the work of a much larger place on the infrastructure of a much smaller one.

It is within this tension, between memory and present, between capacity and demand, that the everyday life of Kottayam unfolds.

At six in the morning, the city is already awake, but not in a hurry.

EVERYDAY LIFE

The day does not begin all at once; it gathers itself in layers. Church bells ring somewhere in the distance, followed by temple chimes, and then the azan. In this overlapping of sound and routine, the city settles into itself—quietly, steadily—before the movement of the day fully begins.

From here, the stories of its people take shape.

Moment 1 – 6:00 AM - 8:30 AM, The slow start | Home courtyard & roadside tea stall | Senior Citizen (Homemaker) / Working Resident

The day begins quietly inside homes.

In a modest courtyard, a senior citizen woman unfolds her newspaper with care. She begins her morning with bed coffee and reading unhurried, deliberate, before the rest of the house stirs. Her routine continues with light exercise, tending to plants, and a short walk along familiar paths. The morning is structured not by urgency, but by repetition: small, steady acts that give shape to time.

Not far away, the same hour takes on a more public rhythm.

At roadside tea stalls, groups of men gather before work. Newspapers are spread across plastic tables, and tea glasses are set down between conversations. Reading here rarely stays silent; headlines become entry points into discussion. Local issues are debated, opinions exchanged, and news is collectively interpreted. The stall becomes both a pause and a platform, where information is not only consumed but shared.

Elsewhere in the city, the morning has already accelerated.

A school teacher has been awake since 5:30 AM, completing household chores, morning prayers, and preparing her daughter for school before leaving on a scooter. Her routine is shaped by anticipation as much as action, of traffic, delays, and the slow unpredictability of the city's roads.

Across interviews, this pattern repeats: mornings are structured around the constraints and rhythms of movement, timing, and responsibility.

Together, these parallel routines: private and public, quiet and conversational, reveal a deeper civic habit. Reading is not an isolated act here; it extends into discussion, into shared spaces, into everyday negotiation. It is this ease of moving between thought and conversation, between home and street, that gives the city its intellectual texture, a quality often reflected in the literary world of writers such as Vaikom Muhammad Basheer, where everyday life and reflection remain inseparable.

EVERYDAY LIFE

Moment 2 – 8:30–10:00 AM, Peak Hours | Baker Junction, KK Road | Young Professional (Architect)

By mid-morning, movement becomes negotiation.

A youth plans her day around congestion, finishing essential travel early, avoiding peak hours, and constantly adjusting.

She explains: *“Many times, I’ve avoided going out just thinking about where to park the car.”*

For others, this negotiation extends to mobility choices. A teacher reflects on her shift from public transport: *“There is no direct bus to the school... I choose the two-wheeler to save time.”* *“Many times, I’ve avoided going out just thinking about where to park the car.”*

What was once shared mobility has slowly become individual problem-solving, each person building their own workaround to the same set of constraints. Movement is no longer just about distance or route, but about prediction, timing, and avoidance.

In this hour, the city is not only moving, it is also being calculated in reverse, from destination to departure, in an attempt to stay ahead of its own congestion.

Moment 3 – 10:00 AM–1:00 PM | Town centre footpaths | Senior Citizen (Shop Owner)/ Pedestrians

By late morning, the heat begins to thin out movement. Many people remain indoors, and the streets slow considerably. Lunch breaks are taken inside schools, offices, and small eateries serving simple, home-style meals. Those who step out move quickly, tracing shaded paths—pausing under trees, awnings, and shopfronts to avoid the harsh sun.

At this hour, the city is less about circulation and more about seeking shelter within its own fabric, moving in fragments between shade, pause, and brief activity.

For those on foot, the city is experienced at a different scale, through the body and its interruptions. A senior citizen shop owner describes walking through town:

“Walking in the city where there are no proper footpaths... walking is not smooth.”

During this time, most people settle into a pause: lunch indoors, rest from the heat, and short errands are kept minimal until the afternoon begins again.

EVERYDAY LIFE

Moment 4 – 3:00–7:00 PM | River edge, residential outskirts | Youth / Senior Citizens

The afternoon belongs to errands, to relatives, and to conversations that unfold along edges and everyday nodes of the city.

For those with evenings free, **Nehru Stadium** becomes one of the few structured open spaces where the day begins to shift again. Digila Anna Mathew recalls going there regularly for running and exercise—the only dedicated track in the city, though now often affected by monsoon flooding and long periods of neglect. She reflects:

“In the past, I used to go to Nehru Stadium every morning for running and exercise.”

There is also an older memory of the city, when it was far more porous. Dr. K.K. Kuruvilla remembers afternoons after school spent in open, unregulated ways, playing football in church courtyards, swimming in the **Meenachil**, or walking into neighbours’ homes without notice.

“There were no ‘No Entry’ signs at any house. You were welcome anywhere,” he recalls.

That form of everyday informality, where space was shared without permission or planning, has gradually narrowed. The river is no longer swimmable, homes are more private, and social life has become more scheduled. For many today, leisure is often reduced to eating out or moving by car, with fewer public systems designed for lingering or play.

Yet the city still holds spaces for gathering.

At **Thirunakkara Maidanam** and around the steps of Thirunakkara Temple, afternoons gather under banyan trees and open edges. Senior citizens return daily for long conversations, while others, people stepping out after work or temple visitors, pause and join in, folding into a shared rhythm where time is not structured but collectively inhabited.

Across the city, small **chaya shops** have emerged as informal commons, especially for the youth. These spaces extend conversations without an agenda, replacing older forms of unstructured public gathering with new, everyday social nodes.

By evening, this informal rhythm intensifies. Young people begin to gather after school and college, using tea shops as unplanned meeting points of return and rest, where chaya and kadi (snacks) and conversations unfold between bites and sips.

At Thali and nearby tea shops, students from multiple colleges arrive, often without coordination. A youth says, “People from three different colleges come here for tea.”

In the same setting, a senior citizen recalls a similar pattern from earlier years: “Back then, we used to go to Thali mostly. It was good to go there to drink tea and talk with friends... We used to sit and talk on the porch of Bishop Close College. It was a safe place to talk with friends.”

A different generation, the same instinct.

Along the riverbanks and ghats, another kind of gathering unfolds. Senior citizens sit facing the water, talking slowly, watching the current, using the river edge as a place to remain rather than pass through. At the same time, groups of young people gather nearby, meeting friends, feeling the wind from the water, and spending unhurried moments together after a long day.

The landscape becomes an informal shared ground across age groups. Even though the river edges are not formally designed for seating, and only a few stepped ghats provide structured access to boats, people adapt the space in their own ways. Some sit on the steps leading down to the water, others on the uneven edges, turning the riverfront into an everyday social space shaped more by use than by design.

Away from these shared spaces, another youth describes her solitude near home. She steps out to the river behind her house when the day becomes overwhelming.

EVERYDAY LIFE

She says, “It’s very peaceful. You can see people going fishing in boats. You can spot many birds there. If you stand there for about 45 minutes, you can see at least ten different types of birds.”

Another youth adds:

“Because of the water, the silence, and the privacy. It feels like a second home to us.”

Here, the city recedes. Water, movement, and silence take over.

When the city becomes heavy, people move to its edges: to Kumarakom, bund roads, paddy fields, and riverbanks, to escape its density.

One resident describes it simply:

“Most of what we did was centred around discovering new places that highlighted the beauty of the backwaters, fields, and nature around us.”

The pattern is consistent across ages and backgrounds. The most restorative moments in Kottayam happen not inside the city, but at its margins. And what this repetition reveals is not only a preference for nature, but a condition of the city itself: when people consistently move outward to find ease, it signals a centre that does not fully hold it.

In *The God of Small Things*, the Kerala landscape carries memory and emotion not as backdrop, but as lived presence. Temple grounds, river edges, maidanams, and tea stalls function as emotional anchors, where the city is not only used, but continuously inhabited through conversation, pause, and return.

As Arundhati Roy writes, the river itself holds this sense of permanence and memory: “The river shrinks, and black crows gorge on bright mangoes in still, dustgreen trees.”

Even in stillness, the landscape is never neutral—it carries time, memory, and life within it.

Moment 5 – 7:00–10:00 PM | Restaurants | Mixed (Youth, Professionals, Families)

The Municipal Vice Chairperson speaks of familiar night-time routines: Chicking and Tandoor, where chilli chicken and parotta become part of repeated family outings. Her children enjoy going there as well. When relatives return from abroad, the outings remain simple: food, a movie, and sometimes short drives to Kumarakom or to Kottayam’s well-known barbecue spots such as Bar-b-que Inn.

A senior citizen, now living in the UK, says that every return home begins the same way. She goes to Thali for a masala dosa, not out of hunger, but as a way of re-entering the city through something familiar, something unchanged.

EVERYDAY LIFE

Another citizen, who spent months here during COVID, remembers her days shaped by small, repeated rituals, local bakeries, thattukadas serving porotta, and evening drives to Kollad to watch the sun sink into the paddy fields.

Across these accounts, **food** becomes more than consumption. It becomes the primary way the city is lived socially. Going out is often structured around eating, and family time is frequently organised around restaurant visits rather than other forms of public leisure. In recent years, a few gastropubs have emerged, but their presence remains limited. For many younger residents, there is a growing sense that the city still lacks a broader night-time public life beyond food spaces, with few alternatives for gathering after evening hours.

A young resident reflects this absence clearly: “There should be a nightlife. People should be able to go out safely even at night. Also, we need more green spaces. While we have places like Kumarakom, it would be great to have good parks and tree-filled spaces within the city.”

Within this limitation, restaurants and eateries quietly take on the role of public infrastructure. They become the city’s default social ground, where families meet, youth gather, and everyday relationships are maintained through the simple act of eating together.

EVERYDAY LIFE

Moment 6 – After 9:00 PM | City-wide | Working Professionals, Women, Elderly

By night, the city withdraws.

A youth observes, “After 8:00 PM, the city feels like it’s getting ready to sleep... There are very few people on the road.”

For some, this emptiness is comfort—a quiet ending to the day. For others, it is a form of constraint. A senior citizen reflects: “After 7 or 8 PM, I doubt if it’s entirely safe for women to walk alone. Street lights don’t work in many places.” Shops close, streets empty out, and movement reduces to necessity. Conversations that once stretched into public spaces fold back into homes. What remains outside is sparse, passing vehicles, scattered lights, and occasional movement that feels temporary rather than continuous.

Night is not an extension of the day here. It is a boundary.

EVERYDAY LIFE

What This Reveals:

Across these moments, a clear pattern emerges: Kottayam is a city where life is highly routinised, but its public realm is largely improvised.

Daily life is not organised around a strong, continuous public infrastructure. Instead, it depends on a network of informal and semi-formal spaces like tea stalls, temple grounds, river edges, stadiums, restaurants, and roadside shade. These are not fully designed as civic commons, yet they consistently become them through repeated use.

Movement through the city is shaped less by openness and more by constraint. Heat, congestion, lack of walkable infrastructure, and limited nighttime safety all influence how and when people move. As a result, daily life is planned backwards, around timing, avoidance, and the negotiation of conditions rather than freedom of movement.

At the same time, social life remains deeply collective. Conversation is a dominant urban practice: in tea shops, on temple steps, along riverbanks, and in residential outskirts. Even leisure is rarely solitary in a strict sense; it is shared, spoken, and situated in familiar places. The city does not offer many formal spaces for this, but people continually produce them through habit.

A second layer of the city exists in memory. Older residents recall a more porous urban condition, one with easier access to land, water, and homes, and fewer restrictions on movement and social interaction. This remembered city still shapes how the present is interpreted, often becoming a quiet benchmark against which change is measured.

What stands out most is a spatial contradiction: while the centre of the city struggles to fully support comfort, safety, and leisure, its edges, riverbanks, paddy fields, backwaters, and peripheral roads—become the primary sites of rest and restoration. People repeatedly move outward to find what the centre does not reliably provide.

Food, in this context, becomes the most stable form of public life. Restaurants and eateries act as informal civic infrastructure, especially in the evenings. They replace the absence of a broader night-time public realm, offering predictable, accessible spaces for gathering across age groups.

Finally, night reveals the city's limit condition. It is not an extended public realm but a withdrawal. Safety concerns, lack of lighting, and limited activity compress public life into earlier hours, reinforcing a daily cycle that ends rather than continues.

Taken together, these patterns reveal a city that is lived intensely but not always supported structurally. Its everyday life is rich in social interaction, but dependent on informal adaptations, memory, and edge spaces to compensate for gaps in design.

EVERYDAY LIFE

If policymakers understood this, they would realise:

The most urgent investments in Kottayam are not spectacular. They would realise that Kottayam's challenge is not a lack of life, but a lack of supported life.

What appears as “informal culture” is, in fact carrying the weight of public infrastructure. Tea shops are not just social habits; they are the city's primary commons. River edges are not recreational design—they are substituted public space. Temple grounds and maidanams are not heritage leftovers—they are functioning civic systems. The city survives socially because people continuously adapt to it, not because it is designed to hold them well.

They would realise that mobility is not only about roads and traffic flow, but about predictability and dignity of movement. A broken footpath is not a minor maintenance issue; it is a daily exclusion. When walking becomes unsafe or uncomfortable, the city quietly decides who gets to move freely and who does not.

They would realise that time in Kottayam is spatially compressed. Life expands in the early morning and evening, and contracts sharply under heat, congestion, and the absence of night infrastructure. This creates a city that is intensely lived in, but unevenly accessible across hours.

They would realise that edges have become more important than centres. The most restorative spaces, riverbanks, paddy fields, backwaters, and bund roads, are not within the planned urban core. This signals not an attraction to “nature,” but a deficit in the city's internal capacity to offer rest, shade, and openness.

They would realise that safety is not only about crime, but about infrastructure reliability. Lighting, walkability, transport availability, and visibility determine whether public life can extend beyond daylight. When these fail, nighttime citizenship shrinks.

They would realise that the real risk is not congestion or growth, but gradual social exit. The younger generation is not rejecting Kottayam, they are constantly negotiating whether it can support the kind of everyday life they want to remain in. That decision is being shaped not by large projects, but by repeated small frustrations.

And finally, they would realise that Kottayam is still in a narrow window of opportunity:

a city where social life is still strong, still visible, still happening in public. But it is being sustained despite systems, not because of them. The question is no longer whether the city is liveable in a general sense, but whether it will choose to make everyday life easier before that quiet attachment to place begins to erode.

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Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging

Every city has places that do more than exist. They hold memory, routine, and relationships that are often felt before they are articulated. In Kottayam, these places are not defined by monumentality or design clarity. They are ordinary landscapes that have absorbed repeated use over time—temple grounds, river edges, roads, campuses, and lakeside stretches.

Belonging here is not produced by planning alone. It is produced through continuity: of returning, sitting, walking the same paths, meeting familiar faces. At the same time, this belonging is uneven. Some spaces remain open and shared, while others are slowly thinning in access, maintenance, or social life. What emerges is not a single map of the city, but a set of emotional geographies—each revealing how Kottayam is lived, remembered, and gradually changing.

1. Thirunakkara Maidanam and Temple Grounds – The Civic Commons

At the centre of Kottayam’s public life lies Thirunakkara Maidanam and the adjoining temple grounds—a rare open civic space embedded in the dense town centre, where everyday life, ritual, and collective memory continuously overlap.

The approach to the temple unfolds through a layered sequence. A gateway opens first into a relatively open forecourt where small shops cluster along the edges—selling flowers, snacks, and offering palm readings—forming a threshold between street and sacred space. From here, the ground gently expands into a larger open maidanam, where people pause, sit, or pass through. At times, cars are parked along its edges, but the central openness remains intact.

This open ground leads toward a long flight of stone steps shaded by mature banyan trees. These trees are not decorative, they structure the experience of the place. People sit on the steps, rest under the canopy, and gather in small informal groups. The transition from open ground to shaded elevation creates a gradual movement toward the temple itself.

At the top sits the Thirunakkara Mahadeva Temple, a nearly 500-year-old Shiva temple built in the traditional Kerala architectural language, timber structures, sloping tiled roofs, and laterite stone elements that reflect climatic and cultural adaptation. The temple is not only a religious structure but a long-standing civic anchor of the city, associated with festivals such as the Thirunakkara Arattu, which brings large-scale public gathering, performance, and ritual activity into the heart of the town.

Together, the temple and maidanam form a continuous public landscape, where sacred, civic, and informal life are not separated but interwoven.

PLACES OF BELONGING

What sustains this space today is not only its history, but its everyday use. Elderly residents arrive in the morning and evening to sit and converse under the banyan shade. Temple visitors pause after worship and remain in conversation. People passing through the city drift into space without planning. The *maidanam* is also a site of collective expression—political meetings, public demonstrations, and informal gatherings continue to take place here. The presence of a stage within the ground reinforces its role as a civic platform as much as a cultural one.

At the entrance, the Gandhi statue marks another layer of meaning, positioning the maidanam as not only a religious forecourt but a democratic public ground. In this sense, it remains one of the few spaces in Kottayam where different social, religious, and political groups continue to share the same physical surface without restriction.

The landscape also plays a climatic and environmental role. The dense banyan canopy and scattered tree cover significantly reduce heat buildup, offering shade and improving microclimatic comfort in an otherwise congested urban core. The openness of the ground provides visual relief in the city centre—a pause in density, movement, and built form.

Economically, the space supports a small but persistent ecosystem of street vendors, festival-related commerce, and temporary stalls during temple events. These informal economies activate the ground during peak periods, especially during the Arattu festival, when the space transforms into a dense field of ritual, trade, and gathering.

Psychologically, the Maidanam functions as a stabilising presence in the city. It is one of the few places where people feel both visible and unhurried, where routine and memory overlap. For many residents, it is not just a site they visit, but a place that anchors their understanding of Kottayam itself.

But beyond its formal history, it is the small repeated acts that give it meaning. An active citizen, the Kathakali artist who has spent his whole life in this city, walks here almost every evening. He does not come to any event or performance.

"More than seeing people, it's the serenity of the Thirunakkara temple that draws me."

Most people in the Maidanam and the temple know him by face. He calls it the place where he feels most himself. A school teacher goes to the temple in the evenings to pray and sit for a while. "Going there in the evening, praying, and sitting for a while gives me peace of mind. It's usually not very crowded."

The municipal vice chairperson still attends the temple festival every year with her family. "Even though we are Christians, we go to see the festival and enjoy the atmosphere. We continue that tradition."

PLACES OF BELONGING

Image: Thirunakkara Mahadeva Temple

A school teacher, walking past in the evening, notices the elderly residents who come from nearby flats just to sit and socialise. The ground holds all of them, different faiths, different ages, different reasons for being there in one shared space.

A youth says, “For me, it would be the temple. Growing up, those ten days of the festival in March were the most exciting. My happiest memories are there. I would really miss it if the temple disappeared.”

What keeps it alive is not infrastructure but habit and memory. At the same time, this landscape faces increasing pressure. Shifts in youth culture toward enclosed commercial spaces, café-based social life, and reduced engagement with open civic grounds are gradually altering patterns of use. Without sustained heritage protection and sensitive urban management, there is a risk of cultural dilution, not through disappearance, but through slow disuse.

The Maidanam is under-maintained, lacking seating, shade, and proper lighting. The Vice Chairperson acknowledges it needs to be redesigned.

A senior citizen worries about what development pressure might bring: "If new buildings are constructed there, it will be a huge loss to Kottayam as we will lose public space."

PLACES OF BELONGING

Image: Thirunakkara Maidanam (During Thirunakkara Mahadeva Temple Utsavam)

What is at stake is not only a physical space, but a civic system. Thirunakkara Maidanam and its temple grounds function as an urban identity marker, a living archive of public life, and one of the last remaining democratic commons in the heart of Kottayam. To lose its continuity would be to weaken not just a landmark, but a key structure of the city's cultural and social memory.

Development here must be careful because this ground carries the civic memory of the entire city, it is the only space in Kottayam where all communities, across religion, politics and class, have historically come together.

PLACES OF BELONGING

2. CMS College Campus

CMS College holds a parallel but very different kind of importance in Kottayam compared to Thirunakkara Maidanam. If Thirunakkara is the city's collective public ground, CMS College is its quieter intellectual and ecological interior, an institution where education, landscape, and memory overlap over time.

Established in 1817, CMS College is one of the oldest Western-style colleges in India, founded by the Church Missionary Society. Its historical significance is not only institutional but spatial. The campus sits close to the town centre, yet the moment one enters it, the density of the city dissolves. Movement slows. Noise reduces. The space opens into long visual corridors of trees, heritage buildings, and shaded pathways.

The architecture itself carries a layered history. The early colonial-era buildings, constructed in stone with high ceilings, verandas, and pitched roofs, were designed for climate as much as for function. They sit within a landscape that has grown over two centuries: large trees planted in the early missionary period now form a continuous canopy, shaping the campus into a shaded ecological system rather than a conventional institutional ground. At its centre lies a preserved green core, almost forest-like, which is rare in a growing town centre.

For students and residents alike, CMS College is not only an educational institution but a place of return. Many describe it as a space they revisit without purpose, just to walk, sit, or experience its atmosphere. The value of the campus lies not in a single function, but in its continuity. It has remained one of the few urban spaces in Kottayam where nature, architecture, and learning coexist at the same scale.

Importantly, CMS College also represents a form of civic memory that is quieter than the Maidanam but equally enduring. Generations of students have passed through its corridors, forming personal and collective histories tied to the place. For many, it is associated with freedom, familiarity, and reflection rather than public performance. It is where the city turns inward.

At the same time, the campus is under subtle pressure. Increasing traffic congestion around its edges has made pedestrian access more difficult. Surrounding development continues to densify, creating a contrast between the protected interior of the campus and the rapidly changing urban fabric outside. While the core remains preserved, its relationship with the city is becoming more strained.

CMS College is therefore not just an academic institution in Kottayam's history. It is a living landscape of learning, memory, and ecology, one of the few places where the city still contains a sense of continuity across time.

PLACES OF BELONGING

A senior citizen describes it without hesitation: "There is a sense of freedom there. There were many trees planted in the old days. With the grass and trees, it has a great atmosphere. Even though it's inside the town, it feels very cool. The architecture is also excellent." Another senior citizen, who did his pre-degree here, says the campus is the place he keeps going back to without planning to. "The campus is very beautiful, old buildings and large beautiful trees planted by the British at that time make the place very aesthetic. I still feel like going back there and studying there once again." A school teacher lists CMS College as her favourite place in all of Kottayam. A youth calls it a major landmark, noting that the institution maintains its old buildings sustainably and preserves the forest in the middle of the city, providing what she calls pure air.

What threatens it is not immediate demolition but the accumulation of pressures around it: the traffic that has made approaching it difficult on foot, the development encroaching on its edges, and the broader pattern in Kottayam of old buildings being replaced without ceremony. Development here must be careful because this campus is one of the few places in the city where nature, history, and civic life coexist at a genuinely human scale, and once its trees are gone, no plan will bring them back.

Image: CMS College

3. Water Edge: The Meenachil River and the Backwaters of Kumarakom

Water in Kottayam is not a distant landscape. It runs through the city's emotional and spatial memory—most powerfully through the Meenachil River, its tributaries, and the wider backwater system that opens into Vembanad Lake and Kumarakom. Unlike a defined landmark or civic ground, water here is continuous. It does not sit inside the city; it structures it.

The Meenachil River passes through and around some of the oldest neighbourhoods of Kottayam, close enough that many residents grew up within walking distance of its banks. For older generations, it is inseparable from everyday life. It was once a place of play, bathing, and informal gathering. A senior citizen recalls this intimacy clearly, "Back then, bathing in the river was a huge delight. The water was clean, there was a flow. After football in the church courtyard, we'd jump into the water and bathe. We did this with a group of ten or twenty friends."

For others, the memory is already transitional. Another senior citizen remembers bathing there as a child with her sisters and friends but notes the change, "now, the river is not as clean, and we don't get the same privacy as before because it's more crowded." What was once an everyday extension of home has slowly become a place of distance.

At Thazhathangadi, where the Meenachil bends through one of Kottayam's oldest settlements, the river takes on an added architectural and cultural weight as a senior citizen recalls, Heritage houses line the banks, their backs turned toward the water, forming a quiet edge between domestic life and landscape. This stretch is closely associated with boat races, seasonal gatherings, and collective viewing. A youth proudly describes, "Thazhathangadi is very special to me, especially because of the boat races. Its heritage and old buildings add significant cultural value. That area definitely needs to be safeguarded." For many residents, it is one of the few places where the city's cultural memory, river ecology, and built heritage overlap in a single frame. As one resident describes, it is not just a scenic location, but a place that produces a feeling of being "exactly where one is meant to be."

A senior citizen says that walking along the Thazhathangadi Meenachil riverbank gives her a feeling she cannot fully explain, just a special feeling, she says, of being exactly where she is supposed to be.

A youth says, "Not for any personal reason, but overall, Thazhathangady feels very special to Kottayam. Its heritage and old buildings add significant cultural value. That area definitely needs to be safeguarded."

PLACES OF BELONGING

Image: Meenachil River Bank

Yet this relationship is under strain. The river today is polluted in many stretches, its banks unevenly maintained, and its access fragmented. Its role as a civic and ecological system has weakened over time. Some imagine a different future, reinforced edges, continuous walkways, public seating, and cafés that reconnect people to the water.

Others frame it more urgently, calling for restoration comparable to cities that have reclaimed their waterways as public infrastructure. What is clear across these perspectives is that the river is no longer simply a natural feature. It is a damaged civic spine, one that once structured daily life, and still holds the potential to do so.

Further from the town centre, the landscape opens into the **backwaters of Kumarakom** and the edges of Vembanad Lake. Here, the scale shifts. The water becomes wider, slower, and more continuous, bordered by coconut groves, paddy fields, and dispersed settlements. Unlike the river within the city, this is a landscape of pause rather than passage.

At the lake's edge, many private clubs and restaurants like **the Sailing Club** and **Kottayam Club** represent one of the few structured points of access to this water system. It is modest in scale, with boats, a lawn, and an uninterrupted horizon of water. For those who use it, the experience is defined not by activity but by stillness. As a youth describes, it is the “water, silence, and privacy” that make it feel like a second home.

PLACES OF BELONGING

Image: Sailing Club, Kumarakom

PLACES OF BELONGING

For others, this relationship extends across generations. Families return to the same edges of the lake over decades, building memory through repetition rather than events. Even during periods of isolation, such as the pandemic, these spaces became essential, places to sit, observe, and remain within the landscape without demand. A citizen recalls, "it's a place my family has been going to for three generations, and the memories built there have become deeply personal over time." She describes going there during COVID, just to sit by the lake and have coffee, as one of the things that made Kottayam feel like itself. A youth says the same of her river, standing there for forty-five minutes, watching fishermen in their boats, counting birds, "it's very peaceful. You can see people going fishing in boats. You can spot many birds there."

But unlike the river, the backwaters are increasingly shaped by access. Much of Kumarakom's waterfront is now privately controlled through resorts, with limited public access to the lake edge. The Sailing Club itself requires membership. What was once a continuous landscape of shared water has become selectively accessible, segmented by ownership and tourism infrastructure. The public walkway along the lakeside that a youth remembers from her childhood has been closed. What should be the city's most democratic natural asset has become selectively available, open only to those who can afford it or who already belong.

This shift marks a quiet transformation. A landscape that once functioned as a shared ecological commons is becoming an enclosed experience. For residents, this is not only a question of tourism or development, but of belonging, of whether the most defining natural system of the region remains open to those who live alongside it.

Across the Meenachil and the backwaters, water in Kottayam holds a dual condition. It is both memory and loss, presence and withdrawal. It is where people once learned to swim, gather, and rest, and where they now return to remember that possibility.

To speak of water here is therefore not only to describe a landscape. It is to describe a shifting relationship between people and their most fundamental public environment, one that is still present, still accessible in parts, but no longer fully shared in the way it once was.

And in that shift lies a larger question for the city: not whether water exists in Kottayam, but whether it still belongs to everyone who lives beside it.

PLACES OF BELONGING

If policymakers understood this, they would realise:

Kottayam is not suffering from a lack of places, but from a lack of continuity between the places that already hold its life together. Its most important civic systems are not newly built infrastructure, but inherited landscapes, Thirunakkara Maidanam, CMS College, the Meenachil River, Thazhathangadi, and the backwaters of Kumarakom, that continue to function as public spaces through habit, memory, and repeated everyday use.

They would realise that these are not “heritage sites” in a static sense, but active civic infrastructures. They hold the city’s social life, ecological comfort, informal economy, and collective memory simultaneously. When people sit under banyan trees, walk through shaded college campuses, gather along river steps, or return to the same lakeside edges, they are not using leisure spaces, they are sustaining the city’s public life in the absence of fully supported ones.

They would realise that the most critical urban issue is not expansion or development pressure alone, but fragmentation. Access to water is narrowing. Walkability is interrupted. Public grounds are under-maintained. Informal commons are carrying more social weight than they were designed for, while formal systems remain underused or inaccessible in everyday terms.

They would realise that what appears as “informal culture” is actually structural dependence. Tea shops replace commons. Temple grounds substitute civic squares. Riverbanks become social parks. College campuses function as ecological refuges. The city continues to work socially, but by compensation rather than design.

They would realise that belonging in Kottayam is still strong, but increasingly fragile. It survives through repetition rather than guarantee. People still return to the same places, still recognise them as theirs, still attach memories to them. But that attachment is being tested by a gradual loss of access, maintenance, and inclusivity.

They would realise that water, in particular, is not just a landscape feature but the city’s original public system, now partially broken. The Meenachil and the backwaters once structured daily life, movement, and leisure. Today, they are unevenly accessible, environmentally stressed, and increasingly privatised at the edges. Restoring them is not beautification, it is restoration of civic continuity.

And finally, they would realise that Kottayam’s most valuable asset is not its growth potential, but its remaining capacity for everyday belonging. The city still holds the social instinct to gather, sit, walk, and return. The question is not whether this instinct exists, but whether the city will continue to support the conditions that allow it to survive.

Because if these ordinary systems weaken further, what is lost will not be individual places, but the ability of the city to hold its own everyday life together.

Voices of Concern

Voices of Concern

There is a particular quality to the frustrations people express about Kottayam. They are not dramatic. They are patient, accumulated, and delivered with the quietness of someone who has said the same thing many times and learned not to expect too much in return. Across 29 interviews, the concerns that emerged were not random grievances, they were patterns, repeated by different people in different circumstances, pointing to the same underlying failures. What follows is an attempt to name them clearly, not just what is wrong, but why it keeps being wrong.

Concern 1: Traffic and Public Transport

Private bus services, which form a major part of intra-city mobility in Kottayam, are frequently overcrowded during peak hours. Commuting becomes a daily exercise in uncertainty—whether a bus will arrive on time, whether it will have space, or whether the journey will even be possible in comfort.

A young resident describes this experience in detail:

“I have tried using public transport. Since going to the gym is a daily activity and I live very close to the centre, buses are available. So I first tried going by bus. But the problem is that only private buses are available, and they are very crowded. Especially coming back after a workout, it's not comfortable at all. If it wasn't this crowded, I would have preferred the bus because it saves money and it's a daily thing. There is always service on that route. But because of people going to work and kids going to school in the morning, there is a huge rush. It's so crowded that there's no room to even prick a needle.”

What emerges is not a lack of transport routes, but a lack of system reliability. Timings are not consistently dependable in daily experience. Even where services exist, they do not function as predictable infrastructure for planning everyday movement. Public transport, instead of being a stabilising system, becomes something residents have to constantly work around.

An active citizen reflects this shift in behaviour: “Due to traffic issues, I mostly use the scooter for travel within the city. Taking a car often leads to parking difficulties. I only take the car for long-distance travel.”

A teacher says, “Definitely the traffic. Getting stuck in traffic when you need to go somewhere urgently is very difficult. It's especially annoying when you're on a two-wheeler in the heat. I hear bypass roads are coming; that would be a huge help.”

As reliability weakens, residents increasingly shift toward private vehicles, not only for comfort, but for predictability. Two-wheelers and cars become the default response to an uncertain public transport system.

This produces a cumulative effect: more private vehicles on the road, higher congestion, greater pressure on limited urban space, and increasing strain on the transport system itself. The system begins to reinforce its own breakdown, where weak public transport pushes private vehicle dependence, and growing private vehicles further reduce the efficiency of movement for everyone.

The concern is consistently raised across residents, from daily commuters to professionals, to transport workers who experience the system from within.

What this reveals to a policymaker:

If read carefully, this is not primarily a “traffic problem.” It is a system reliability problem.

A policymaker should understand three core things:

1. People are not rejecting public transport; they are adapting to its unpredictability.

The shift to private vehicles is not preference-led; it is reliability-led. When timing, comfort, and capacity cannot be depended on, people individually optimise for certainty.

VOICES OF CONCERN

2. Fragmented operations are creating system failure even where services exist

The issue is not the absence of buses or routes. It is the absence of a coordinated system where:

- Frequency is dependable
- Capacity matches peak demand
- Timing is predictable enough for daily planning

Without this, availability does not translate into usability.

3. Congestion is a downstream effect, not the root problem

Traffic is not the cause—it is the outcome of systemic breakdown in shared mobility. Treating congestion alone does not resolve the underlying shift toward private transport.

They should:

- Start treating public transport as a timed system, not just a network of routes
- Prioritise predictability over expansion alone
- Align peak-hour capacity with real commuter flows (school + work cycles)
- Recognise that transport policy is also behavioural policy: people respond to trust in systems

The core shift required is this: from “availability of buses” to “dependability of movement.”

Concern 2: City that cannot be walked

Stand at Baker Junction or Shastri Road at 8:30 AM and observe how pedestrians move through Kottayam. They step off broken footpaths onto the road, weave between two-wheelers, pause at unpredictable gaps in traffic, and proceed by reading vehicle movement rather than following any continuous pedestrian path. Along KK Road, Bakery Junction, and Shastri Road, footpaths are uneven, intermittently blocked, occupied by vendors, or rendered unusable by parked vehicles. Walking in the centre of Kottayam is therefore not a continuous condition but a fragmented negotiation with traffic.

A senior citizen notes the everyday difficulty directly: “Walking in the city where there are no proper footpaths... walking is not smooth.”

A young resident adds: “For handicapped individuals or children, Kottayam might be difficult. The walkways aren't proper. Navigating through poorly constructed footpaths requires extra care.”

VOICES OF CONCERN

The concern is consistently raised across almost every category of resident, from the Municipal Chairperson, who references Bangalore's Jayanagar as a model for pedestrian-oriented planning, to shop owners who have witnessed accidents outside their premises.

This persistence points to a condition that is not isolated but structural. Responsibility for pedestrian infrastructure is split between the Municipality and the PWD, where implementation can be requested but not enforced. At the same time, municipal wards operate with limited annual budgets, a large portion of which is consumed by maintenance, leaving minimal scope for systemic redesign.

Planning capacity further reinforces this condition. In many municipalities in Kerala, including Kottayam, transport and spatial decisions are often led by civil engineers rather than urban planners. This tends to prioritise road expansion and traffic movement over integrated mobility planning, where walking, public transport, and street design are treated as a single system.

Until a bypass meaningfully reduces through-traffic in the town centre, and until public transport becomes reliably timed, comfortable, and predictable enough to function as a daily system of dependence rather than uncertainty, incremental improvements to footpaths alone will not restore walkability.

The core issue is therefore not only the absence of infrastructure, but the absence of a coordinated mobility system. Walking, buses, and shared transport currently operate as separate, unaligned layers rather than a unified network of movement.

What residents consistently recall is not simply better infrastructure, but a different condition of the city, one where movement was easier to anticipate, easier to share, and easier to trust.

VOICES OF CONCERN

What this reveals to a policymaker:

What is being seen here is not a series of broken footpaths, but a city where walking stops and starts repeatedly, forcing people onto the road simply to continue moving.

The problem is not isolated locations: it is **discontinuity**. A stretch may be repaired, but it does not connect safely to the next. At junctions, markets, and bus stops, the pedestrian path quietly disappears. Movement becomes something improvised rather than supported.

Responsibility is also split. Different agencies handle different stretches, so no one is accountable for the experience of walking from one end to another. The result is a network that exists on paper, but not in lived experience.

And beneath this lies a planning choice: roads are treated as the main system, while footpaths are treated as leftover space. So they shrink, get blocked, or simply end where space becomes convenient for vehicles.

For a policymaker, the takeaway is simple. This is not about repairing footpaths. It is about whether the city allows a person to move from one place to another without interruption, without stepping into traffic, without constantly negotiating safety.

Concern 3: A city losing its young people

Across interviews, there is a quiet agreement that young people are unlikely to stay in Kottayam. The reasons are not singular, they accumulate. Limited entry points into the local economy, absence of startup or MNC ecosystems, and a job market largely shaped by established family-run structures make it difficult for newcomers to build independent careers.

But the decision to leave is not driven by employment alone. Many describe a comparison that extends beyond income: better-paying opportunities, more diverse work environments, and a stronger sense of upward mobility outside the city. Alongside this is a different kind of pull, cities elsewhere offering a more visible social life, larger peer networks, and a greater sense of anonymity and freedom.

“I highly doubt it. Social life is nil. Job opportunities are very low... To function as a human being, it's not a great place.” – A youth

“Generally, businesses in Kottayam flourish if there is family backing... There is no MNC or startup culture here.” – Digila Anna Mathew, Lawyer.

There is also a quieter social shift. As more young people leave, those who remain often feel a shrinking peer circle, fewer shared spaces, and a reduced sense of a young public culture. The departure of peers becomes self-reinforcing—each exit makes staying feel more isolated.

VOICES OF CONCERN

This concern persists because migration is no longer just economic, it is comparative. It is shaped by better opportunities elsewhere, more active public life, greater social exposure, and a sense that life outside offers both privacy and possibility in ways the city currently does not.

This concern persists because economic opportunity and urban quality of life are interlinked. Young people do not leave only for jobs, they leave because the absence of jobs is compounded by the absence of social life, public spaces, and the basic civic infrastructure that makes a city worth living in as a young adult.

This pattern is reflected in broader data. The Kerala Migration Survey 2023 estimates 35,382 student emigrants from Kottayam, the third highest in the state, with student migration from Kerala nearly doubling between 2018 and 2023. The South First The Kerala High Court has specifically identified the absence of adequate infrastructure and the lack of aesthetic appeal in Kerala's cities as reasons behind young people relocating. Globalmediajournal A young Kottayam resident now living in Australia told The News Minute in 2023 that the infrastructure development in Kerala was slow and that she could build a better life in a shorter span of time abroad.

A young resident now in Australia described how slower infrastructure development and faster life progression abroad made leaving a more viable choice.

What this reveals to a policymaker:

This concern is a cumulative outcome of how a city performs in everyday life compared to elsewhere.

First, young people are not leaving only because opportunities are absent, but because opportunities elsewhere feel more accessible, structured, and open to newcomers. The issue is not just the quantity of jobs, but who can enter them and how easily.

Second, migration is increasingly shaped by comparison. Careers, income, social life, and personal freedom are no longer judged within the city, but against a wider field of cities and possibilities. Kottayam is not being evaluated in isolation, it is being measured against alternatives that appear faster, more open, and more diverse.

Third, there is a compounding social effect. As more young people leave, the remaining population experiences reduced peer networks, fewer informal spaces, and a thinning of shared youth culture. This makes staying feel progressively less viable, reinforcing the cycle of departure.

For a policymaker, the key insight is this: youth retention is not only an economic problem. It is an urban condition problem, shaped by how open the city is to newcomers, how much social life it sustains, and how confidently it allows young people to imagine a future within it.

VOICES OF CONCERN

A youth also shares, “I wish they would remove that Skywalk. It was a decent green space in the centre of town that they removed in the name of development. Also, since Kottayam isn't a massive city, having more trees would be great.”

Another youth says, “That incomplete skywalk. It was a bad idea, and it's an eyesore. I don't know how many years it's been like that. I wish someone would just give up on it and remove it. Beyond a political agenda, I don't think it serves any good purpose. People don't use skywalks. Even if you put escalators, it's a hard bargain to make the public use them. I detest the skywalk.”

This concern persists because the skywalk is not an isolated failure, it is a pattern. Projects are inaugurated. Funds run short. Political ownership shifts. The structure remains. This is how public trust in governance erodes, not through dramatic failure but through the slow accumulation of things that were promised and never delivered.

Image: Seematti Roundabout Skywalk

VOICES OF CONCERN

What this reveals to a policymaker:

This is not about a single unfinished structure. It is about how public projects move through the city without ever fully arriving. A space is altered, a promise is made visible, but completion slips across departments, budgets, and political cycles until what remains is neither usable infrastructure nor the original place.

For a policymaker, the issue is not construction alone, but continuity. When execution is fragmented, the city accumulates half-finished decisions that reshape public space without delivering public value. Over time, these become more visible than completed works.

The deeper implication is simple: infrastructure is not judged at the moment of announcement or foundation, but at the point where responsibility ends. In this gap between intent and completion, public trust is quietly built or steadily lost.

Concern 4: A city flooding every year

Every monsoon, the Meenachil River overflows. Roads in low-lying areas fill with water. Residents absorb the damage individually and wait for the water to recede. This is not a new pattern, the Meenachil is described as one of Kerala's most treacherous rivers due to flash floods, with serious ongoing issues including pollution from urban waste, illegal sand mining, reducing water table levels, and loss of tree cover, decreasing the river's water retention capacity (Source: [Wikipedia](#)). As recently as May 2022, the Meenachil's banks were breached at multiple points, flooding parts of Pala and Erattupeta, with water flowing over the danger mark at the Erattupetta causeway and Aruvithura College bridge (Source: [Onmanorama](#))

The causes are well understood, such as encroachments on rivers and canals, the filling of paddy fields with soil, and the tiling of courtyards that prevents rainwater from percolating into the ground. The solutions are also understood. What has been missing is the consistent political will to implement them.

"Flooding is a major issue here. Proper measures should be taken to drain the water. But nothing happens here. The residents have to do it ourselves. Many people have complained over the years, but no action has been taken." – A youth

"The drains from the city, including waste from the Medical College and District Hospital, flow directly into the Meenachil River." – Municipal Clean City Manager.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Flooding in Kottayam is not an unexpected natural event, but a recurring condition shaped over decades. It emerges from accumulated land-use decisions, encroachment on waterways, loss of wetlands, blocked canals, and surfaces that prevent natural absorption. The causes are already known; the challenge lies in addressing them.

What makes this persistent is not technical uncertainty, but governance fragmentation. Rivers, drainage systems, land regulation, and waste management fall under different jurisdictions, yet their impacts converge in the same spaces and the same seasons. Responsibility is divided, but consequences are shared.

What this reveals to a policymaker:

For a policymaker, the core insight is this: flooding is not a single-sector problem. It is the outcome of long-term planning decisions that have reduced the river's capacity to function, combined with weak enforcement over time. The system is not lacking information, it is lacking sustained coordination and follow-through.

What this reveals is that the issue is not understanding what needs to be done, but the inability to consistently do it across departments, land pressures, and political cycles.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Concern 5: The environment no one is protecting

Kottayam sits within one of Kerala's most ecologically rich landscapes, and yet what residents describe is a gradual thinning of that environment. Paddy fields are being filled for construction, tree cover is reduced for road expansion, and the Meenachil River carries increasing traces of plastic and untreated waste. Alongside this, residents also describe a noticeable rise in local temperatures and loss of shade in everyday movement.

“Reclaiming paddy fields and wetlands is a huge mistake. This will lead to major flooding in the future. Trees are being cut down to widen roads. Shady roads are nowhere to be seen today.” – An active citizen

“Development should happen without affecting biodiversity. Natural resources like rivers and lakes should be dealt with sensitively.” – Youth

The greenery and natural beauty of Kottayam must be maintained. When development comes, reclaiming paddy fields and cutting down trees should be minimised. Our cultural heritage and old buildings should also be protected. – An active citizen

At a policy level, environmental protection has already been articulated. A “Green City” vision exists, including tree planting, protection of water bodies, and discouraging hard paving of open surfaces. The gap lies not in articulation, but in enforcement and continuity across time.

At the same time, residents point to a quieter but critical layer: everyday environmental behaviour. Waste entering rivers, plastic accumulation, and untreated household and commercial discharge continue to affect the Meenachil. This is not only an infrastructure issue but also a civic one, where public spaces like rivers are still treated as disposal systems rather than shared ecological assets.

What this reveals to a policymaker is that environmental decline in Kottayam is not the result of a single policy gap, but the combined effect of land-use decisions, weak enforcement, and limited civic responsibility. Protection of the environment here depends not only on regulation from above, but also on public awareness that ecological systems are shared and fragile.

Without both institutional enforcement and civic ownership, the same cycle continues, where the environment is acknowledged as valuable, but not consistently protected in practice.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Concern 6: Safety in public spaces at night

Across interviews, women describe a city that becomes difficult to inhabit after dark, especially alone. The concern is not limited to isolated incidents, but to a broader shift in how public space behaves at night, streets feel empty, poorly lit, and largely unaccommodating to pedestrian presence.

“After 7 or 8 PM, I doubt if it's entirely safe for women to walk alone. Street lights don't work in many places.” –, Senior Citizen

“People are overly concerned about our lives, who we go out with, what we wear, and why we aren't married yet.” – Youth

Alongside infrastructure gaps like inconsistent lighting and limited late-night mobility options, there is also a social dimension that shapes behaviour in public space. Women describe being observed differently when they are outside at night, where their presence itself is often read as unusual or questioned.

In practice, this creates a city where nighttime public life is minimal. Streets are largely dominated by vehicles, while pedestrian activity becomes rare. The absence of others on the street reinforces a sense of isolation, making movement feel more visible and more scrutinised.

What this reveals to a policymaker is that safety at night is not defined only by crime or infrastructure, but by how normal it feels for different groups to be present in public space. In Kottayam, both conditions, physical infrastructure like lighting and transport, and social acceptance of women in public after dark, operate together.

Until both are addressed, public space remains functionally incomplete after a certain hour, not because people are explicitly excluded, but because presence itself feels out of place.

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Concern 7: Waste that goes nowhere

Kottayam's waste problem is not experienced as a single visible crisis, but as a daily accumulation in small, repeated moments: plastic piling up in front of shops, waste dumped in vacant plots, and stagnant collection points where garbage is gathered but not fully processed. Residents also point to pollution entering the Meenachil River and persistent localised issues like foul-smelling stretches near market areas.

In Swachh Survekshan 2023, Kottayam ranked 394th nationally, below all other major Kerala cities, reflecting a measurable gap in urban cleanliness standards (Source: [Kerala Kaumudi](#)). Residents describe what drives that number in their own terms: plastic piling up in front of shops after Haritha Karma Sena workers collect it, but before the municipality picks it up from the collection point.

Waste is dumped in vacant plots. Raw hospital drainage is entering the Meenachil. The smell near the Kodimatha market area in the morning.

"I don't think anyone takes waste management seriously. People often dump waste in vacant plots. If they see a place as uninhabited, it gets misused." – Youth

A citizen says, "Traffic and waste management are problems that many people are aware of, but they are not always addressed in a serious or long-term way."

A 55-crore CNG plant is under construction at Vadavathoor with World Bank support, and a 13-crore Resource Facilitation Centre for inorganic waste sorting is being established – significant investments that signal institutional intent. But the last-mile failure – waste collected and then abandoned before it reaches processing – remains the persistent gap. This concern persists because waste management requires continuous coordination between the Municipality, service workers, and citizens, and the weakest link in that chain determines the outcome for everyone.

What this reveals to a policymaker is that the issue is not the absence of systems, but the break in continuity within them. Waste is being collected, partially sorted, and partially transported, but the chain fails at the point where coordination between municipality, service workers, and processing infrastructure is required to remain uninterrupted.

In effect, responsibility is distributed, but completion is not owned. And in that gap, waste does not disappear—it simply relocates within the city.

VOICES OF CONCERN

VOICES OF CONCERN

Waste is dumped in vacant plots. Raw hospital drainage is entering the Meenachil. The smell near the Kodimatha market area in the morning.

What does this reveal?

What these concerns collectively reveal is that Kottayam is not struggling with isolated urban problems, but with a fragmented system of governance where mobility, environment, safety, and infrastructure are managed in parts rather than as a whole. Most issues raised across interviews already have known technical solutions; what is missing is sustained coordination, clear accountability, and continuity across administrative cycles.

Traffic and mobility sit at the centre of this condition. Roads are congested not only because of increasing vehicles, but because pedestrian infrastructure is weak, public movement is unreliable, and private vehicle dependence has become the default response to system failure. The result is a city where movement is constantly negotiated rather than smoothly enabled.

What is systemic includes: delayed infrastructure decisions such as the bypass, fragmented responsibilities between agencies like the PWD and Municipality, limited planning capacity, constrained ward-level funding, weak enforcement of environmental regulation, and an uncoordinated mobility system that produces congestion and inefficiency as secondary outcomes.

What is incidental includes: potholes, broken slabs, isolated waste dumping, or temporary maintenance lapses: visible symptoms that often receive attention, while the structural causes remain unchanged.

Across all concerns, whether flooding, waste, safety, or traffic, the pattern is consistent: problems persist not because they are unknown, but because they are not sustained through implementation. Responses remain reactive and cyclical, often tied to election periods or short-term interventions, rather than long-term system design.

The deeper gap, therefore, is not between problems and solutions, but between planning and execution. Kottayam's lived reality points to a city where governance is aware of that needs to change, but not yet structured to carry that change across time.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow

When people in Kottayam speak about the future, they do not describe transformation in dramatic terms. They describe repairs. The dreams come from daily friction—walking on broken footpaths, waiting for unreliable buses, watching the river flood, or seeing familiar places remain unfinished for years. Because of this, their aspirations are measured. They are shaped less by the imagination of a different city and more by the desire for a functioning one.

These futures are not abstract. They are spoken by those who already live with the city as it is: a municipal chairperson looking at planning constraints, an architect comparing cities she has worked in, a shop owner navigating traffic daily, a student considering whether to leave, and older residents who remember when certain systems still worked more smoothly.

Across these voices, seven consistent directions emerge.

Hope 1: A city with less traffic and better managed movement

A recurring concern across interviews is not only congestion within Kottayam, but the fact that a significant portion of the traffic passing through the town does not actually belong to it. Vehicles moving between neighbouring districts often cut through the urban core, concentrating pressure on already narrow roads and intersections.

Residents describe daily movement as slow and unpredictable, shaped more by traffic build-up than by distance. This is visible at junctions like Baker Junction and Shastri Road, where movement is frequently interrupted by mixed flows of local, inter-district, and heavy vehicles competing for the same limited road space.

A citizen recalls her dream for Kottayam, "In the future, I would hope to see improvements that make everyday life more convenient and organised. This could include better parking spaces, improved waste management systems, and services like Uber that make transportation easier"

An active citizen expresses, "It doesn't need to be like Kochi; it's enough to remain a small city with good roads, bridges and overbridges"

Another youth says, "We need better connectivity, like in Kochi, but we should also preserve the old town charm with less pollution and more trees."

A councillor dreams of, "Kottayam needs a total overhaul. If the M.C. Road development is implemented as planned, it will bring a big change. We need bypasses and ring roads that allow travel without entering the town centre. Only flyovers or tunnels can solve the traffic issue."

Across these perspectives, a shared direction emerges: a bypass system that functions effectively enough to divert through-traffic away from the town centre, allowing the city core to function primarily for local movement rather than transit flow.

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Alongside this, residents point to the need for a more reliable public transport system. The reliance on private vehicles is not framed as a preference, but as an adaptation to congestion and uncertainty. When travel times are unpredictable and road space is saturated, individual mobility becomes the only dependable option available.

What people are asking for is not expansion, but rebalancing:

- Bypass routes that carry inter-district traffic outside the core city
- Reduced congestion within central junctions
- Public transport system that is reliable enough to serve as a real alternative to private vehicles

This is a structural reorganisation of movement rather than a cosmetic upgrade, so that Kottayam functions less as a transit corridor and more as a city where internal mobility is consistent, predictable, and shared.

This hope is not new. It has been discussed for decades. What remains unresolved is not the idea itself, but its completion.

Hope 2: Streets that can be walked safely

For many residents, the most immediate aspiration is not expansion, but basic continuity of movement. Architects and daily commuters alike describe a city where walking is possible only in fragments, interrupted by vehicles, parking, and broken edges.

A youth frames it simply: “Kottayam is actually a walkable city. It only needs shaded streets and proper walkways.”

An auto driver points to lived experience rather than planning language: walking and driving have become competing systems in the same narrow space. The Municipal Chairperson looks at Jayanagar and MG road in Bangalore and sees a replicable model: excellent footpaths that encourage walking rather than vehicle use.

What people are asking for is not pedestrian zones in a large-city sense, but something more basic: uninterrupted, shaded footpaths on key roads like KK Road and Shastri Road, and traffic reduced enough that walking is not constantly negotiated.

This is a realistic intervention, but it depends on coordination between road agencies, local body maintenance, and traffic regulation, rather than isolated repair work. This hope can remain alive if the Municipality and PWD resolve their jurisdictional division over footpaths, and if the bypass is built to divert through-traffic, because without reduced vehicle volume, no footpath investment will create a genuinely walkable town centre.

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Hope 3: A park that is open

From youth to teachers to senior citizens, the wish for a functioning public park appears with quiet persistence. Not a grand park – just the municipal park, open, maintained, and accessible in the evenings. "My biggest wish is for a good public park. A place where we can spend time with family in the evenings. Right now, apart from going for a movie, there are very few places to take children," says a teacher. A youth is direct: "Just opening that municipal park would be enough. Whatever park it is, if it's open to the public, it will be a big relief."

This hope can remain alive if the Municipality completes the park renovation with a publicly committed timeline, and if maintenance is treated as recurrent infrastructure spending rather than discretionary expenditure.

An active citizen stresses the importance of leisure spaces, "Leisure is as important as food, clothing, and shelter. But what do we have here for that? There isn't even a good park. I have been to Australia; do you know how beautifully they develop their resources? In every area, there are facilities for leisure. What do we have here?"

Another active citizen wants, "People need to feel that it is their own necessity. When they develop a mindset for entertainment and relaxation, they will realise it brings mental freshness, which in turn affects their work. Taking the example of a park, if we get a little free time to just sit and talk, it refreshes the mind and even benefits one's professional life, especially for those with high-pressure jobs. When they feel that benefit, they will want such things to be developed. There's no point in just building a park; everything there must be maintained. Once people understand the need for it, the concept of mental freshness is gaining popularity now, but people usually opt for long trips. The current trend is to go to Munnar or other distant places to enjoy. But we have places right next to us. When more people start visiting local spots, they will realise the value and keep coming back. They just need to understand the need. The youth understand this, especially those working in Technopark or Infopark; when the workload gets heavy, they realise the necessity of entertainment time."

Another adds that the absence of such a space limits even simple social routines like spending time outdoors with children.

This is not a demand for a new landscape, but for activation of an existing one, opening, maintaining, and ensuring predictable access. The feasibility is high, but it depends on whether maintenance is treated as a continuous responsibility rather than an occasional intervention.

Hope 4: Young people who stay

Every generation of interviewee, from senior citizens who watched their children leave, to young professionals on the edge of leaving themselves, to councillors governing a city emptying of its youth, names the same dream: conditions that make staying possible. The Municipal Chairperson's vision of Kottayam as an education hub is the most structured articulation: more colleges, a private sector education economy, students who stay to study and then stay to work.

Kerala's Finance Minister acknowledged in his 2023 budget speech the need to retain the state's youth by creating more job opportunities and better facilities (Source: Globalmediajournal).

A youth frames it as a planning problem: "If you have a better-planned city, people might stay. Whether it's government projects or subsidies, there should be encouragement from the government side."

Another youth dreams, "I wish for Kottayam to become more high-tech. More job opportunities in the IT sector should come here. Only then will our younger generation stay. Right now, everyone leaves as soon as they finish their studies. There should be circumstances for them to work here itself. Also, there should be planned development to reduce the crowd in the town."

This hope can remain alive if economic development and urban quality of life are treated as the same project, because young people do not leave only for jobs, they leave because the absence of jobs compounds with the absence of everything else, like social life, a better lifestyle and other people to socialise with and their freedom.

Hope 5: The waterfronts restored and developed

The river appears in the dreams as consistently as it appears in the memories. The Municipal Chairperson wants Kottayam to do what Singapore has done: boat services, reinforced banks, and public walkways along the river. A senior citizen wants cafés, spaces for children, and proper railings along the banks. An active citizen wants the Old Seminary banks to become what they already are in his imagination, a quiet, accessible civic space for evening sitting.

"We should transform the Meenachil River just as countries like Singapore protect their rivers. Facilities like boat services there should come here as well." – Municipal Chairperson.

Another senior citizen focuses on the scope of tourism, "There is a lot of scope for tourism in Kottayam, with places like Kumarakom nearby. But these are not well-maintained"

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Another senior citizen says, “I want Kottayam to develop a lot. There should be good roads and better transportation facilities. At the same time, we must be careful to protect our environment. I wish to see the Meenachil River and the backwaters with clear water, just like in the old days. My dream is a clean and safe Kottayam.”

An active citizen says, “Kottayam has many water bodies. Development should happen there, but not by destroying existing resources. When developing waterfronts, it should be done without losing their originality. That originality is the value of our land.”

This hope can remain alive if encroachments are addressed systematically and there is civic awareness among people to not pollute our waters, if hospital drainage is redirected to treatment plants, and if the riverfront is treated as civic infrastructure rather than unused land.

Hope 6: A city safe at night for everyone and accessible to all

Women across interviews describe the same quiet dream, a city where they can move after 8 PM without calculating risk. A street light that works. A bus that comes. A ride-hailing service that operates.

A teacher articulates it for everyone: "I want Kottayam to be a place where women and children can walk without fear, even at night."

A youth wants an active exercise culture, cycling, and walking tracks available throughout the day.

Another youth wants a place for young people to gather that does not close at nine.

Another youth hopes for, “There should be a nightlife. People should be able to go out safely even at night. Also, we need more green spaces. While we have places like Kumarakom, it would be great to have good parks and tree-filled spaces within the city.”

This hope can remain alive if street lighting is treated as a maintenance priority, if ride-hailing services are formally brought into Kottayam, and if public spaces that make nighttime presence feel ordinary, parks and lit walkways, are created and kept open.

Hope 7: A green city

The Municipal Chairperson has articulated a Green City vision – shade trees and fruit-bearing trees planted across the town, courtyards that breathe, a city that does not repeat Bangalore's water crisis. Cherian P. Kurien warns that filling paddy fields will flood the city. Mariah Vellapally wants development that preserves biodiversity. Tita Tegi wants trees on every street, protected by law.

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"Our vision is to transform Kottayam into a 'Green City'. We will plant more shade trees and fruit-bearing trees like jackfruit and mango within the town." –Municipal Chairperson

A youth hopes for, " While we have places like Kumarakom, it would be great to have good parks and tree-filled spaces within the city.

A senior citizen hopes for a cleaner Kottayam, " Kottayam should become cleaner."

An Active citizen wants, "The greenery and natural beauty of Kottayam must be maintained. When development comes, reclaiming paddy fields and cutting down trees should be minimised. Our cultural heritage and old buildings should also be protected."

This hope can remain alive if tree planting is matched with tree protection, if the trees on Shastri Road, at CMS College, and along the Collectorate are given legal protection equivalent to a listed building, and if new development is conditioned on maintaining green cover.

Conditions for Hope

What must change: The bypass must be built. The PWD-Municipality split on footpath accountability must be resolved. Ward budgets must be supplemented for structural projects. The municipal park must open. Formal civic participation must be institutionalised.

What is practical in five years: A walkable Shastri Road extended to two or three additional central streets. The municipal park was reopened and maintained. Riverfront walkways at Thazhathangadi and the Old Seminary banks. A public forum meeting is held quarterly with publicised outcomes. Ride-hailing services operational in the city.

What requires structural reform: The bypass, requiring state-level funding sustained across governments. Economic diversification requires a policy decision to attract educational institutions and knowledge-sector employers. Environmental protections – requiring regulatory enforcement that currently does not consistently happen. Kerala's urban planning shortage – producing 100 planners a year while needing 900 – means that without investment in planning capacity, cities like Kottayam will continue to be governed by infrastructure responses that react to problems rather than anticipate them (Source: [Centre for Public Policy Research](#))

Who is responsible: The Municipality for parks, footpaths, trees, civic forums, and waste management. The PWD for roads and drainage. The state government for the bypass, Meenachil restoration, and economic development strategy. Citizens for the courtyards they tile, the waste they dump, and the civic forums they do or do not attend.

DREAMS FOR TOMORROW

Reflection

What stands in the way of Kottayam realising its dreams is not the absence of vision, the interviews are full of vision, from the Municipal Chairperson's Green City plan to Meenakshi's town hall proposal to Unnikrishnan's open public space. What stands in the way is the absence of continuity. Plans change with governments. Projects are inaugurated and stall. The bypass has been discussed for thirty years. The municipal park has been under renovation for years with no completion date. The skywalk at Central Junction has been an unfinished, rusted structure since 2016, reduced from an ambitious infrastructure project to, as one reporter observed, an eyesore and a meme. (Source: [The South First](#))

What Kottayam's residents are asking for, across ages, backgrounds, and the length of 29 interviews, is not a spectacular city. They are asking for a city that follows through. A city that finishes what it starts. A city where the park opens when they say it will open, the footpath is fixed when they say it will be fixed, and the river is cleaned before the next monsoon fills it again with what was promised would be treated. They are not asking for a miracle. They are asking for the ordinary reliability of a city that means what it says. That is the dream. And it is, in the end, an achievable one – if the political will to sustain it can be found and held.

Policy Insights

Policy Insights:

What the city is telling us?

This section brings together insights emerging across interviews, observations, and spatial readings of Kottayam. When viewed together, these narratives do not describe isolated urban issues, but a set of structural patterns shaping how the city functions, how people move through it, and how public life is gradually being reorganised.

The aim here is to translate lived experience into governance insight: identifying where systems break down, where informal solutions compensate, and where small, targeted interventions could significantly improve everyday urban life.

1. Mobility, Traffic, and Urban Circulation

Across interviews, mobility emerges as one of the most immediate constraints on daily life. However, the issue is not simply congestion, it is misdirected movement.

A large proportion of traffic in Kottayam is not destination-based but through-traffic between districts, cutting through the town centre and overwhelming internal roads. This creates a condition where the city functions simultaneously as a destination and a corridor.

Key stress points include Baker Junction, Shastri Road, and KK Road, where mixed flows of inter-district vehicles, local traffic, and heavy vehicles intersect without separation.

What this reveals:

- Kottayam lacks a functional bypass hierarchy separating local and regional movement.
- Road expansion inside the city is repeatedly attempted, but cannot resolve structural flow issues.
- Movement is increasingly based on avoidance, timing, and prediction, not efficiency.

Public experience:

Residents describe planning their day backwards from congestion rather than distance. Travel is no longer linear—it is negotiated.

Policy direction:

- **Short-term:** Improve junction management, parking control, and signal coordination at key nodes.
- **Medium-term:** Strengthen intra-city public transport reliability (frequency, last-mile coverage).

POLICY INSIGHTS

Long-term: Develop functional bypass and ring-road systems to divert inter-district traffic away from the core city.

Key stakeholders:

PWD Kerala, Municipal Corporation, State Transport Department, and regional planning authorities.

2. Fragmented Governance and Maintenance Systems

A recurring structural issue is the fragmentation of responsibility between institutions, especially between the Municipality and PWD.

Footpaths, drainage, roads, and waterways are managed by different agencies, but experienced by citizens as a single system. This disconnect produces visible breakdowns in maintenance continuity.

What this reveals:

- No single accountable authority for the integrated urban experience.
- Maintenance is episodic rather than continuous.
- Infrastructure is treated as project-based, not system-based.

Policy direction:

- Establish an inter-agency urban coordination unit for mobility, drainage, and public space.
- Create ward-level maintenance budgets tied to performance metrics.
- Introduce continuity tracking for infrastructure lifecycle (not just project completion).

3. Public Space Dependence on Informality

Kottayam's public life is strong, but structurally unsupported. Tea shops, temple grounds, river edges, stadiums, and campus spaces function as de facto civic infrastructure.

What this reveals:

- The city's "commons" are mostly informal or inherited spaces, not designed for civic infrastructure.
- Social life persists because people continuously adapt spaces to their needs.
- Formal public spaces are limited, under-maintained, or inconsistently accessible.

POLICY INSIGHTS

Policy direction:

- Upgrade informal commons with basic infrastructure (shade, seating, lighting) without over-formalisation.
- Protect and legally recognise key public grounds (e.g., Maidanams, river ghats).
- Design small-scale distributed public spaces instead of large centralised parks alone.

4. Environmental Stress and Urban Commons Degradation

Water systems, wetlands, and green cover form the ecological base of Kottayam, but are under increasing pressure from encroachment, waste disposal, and land conversion.

The Meenachil River, once a shared public system, now shows visible fragmentation in access and ecological health.

What this reveals:

- Environmental systems are still central to daily life, but no longer well-protected.
- Waste management gaps (especially last-mile failures) directly affect water bodies.
- Loss of paddy fields and wetlands increases flood vulnerability.

Policy direction:

- Strengthen enforcement of wetland and river buffer protections.
- Integrate waste management chain (collection → transport → processing accountability).
- Launch citizen-linked river stewardship programs at the ward level.

5. Safety, Night-Time Accessibility, and Gendered Mobility

Night-time in Kottayam is marked by withdrawal rather than extension. Public life reduces sharply after 8–9 PM.

Concerns are both infrastructural (lighting, transport availability) and social (surveillance, behavioural judgement).

What this reveals:

- Safety is shaped by visibility, continuity, and activity, not only policing.
- Lack of night-time infrastructure limits women's and youth mobility.
- The city lacks a functioning 24-hour civic layer.

POLICY INSIGHTS

Policy direction:

- Repair and standardise street lighting networks.
- Enable night-time public transport options and ride availability.
- Activate select public spaces for safe evening use (parks, riverfronts, corridors).

6. Ecological and Spatial Imbalance: Centre vs Edge

A consistent pattern emerges: people move outward to find comfort. Riverbanks, Kumarakom backwaters, paddy fields, and bund roads become primary restorative spaces, while the urban core is congested, hot, and fragmented.

What this reveals:

- The city centre lacks shade, rest, and ecological comfort.
- Edges function as a substitute public infrastructure.
- There is a spatial mismatch between where life happens and where comfort exists.

Policy direction:

- Introduce continuous shade-tree corridors in core streets.
- Develop inner-city blue-green networks (water + tree systems).
- Reconnect riverfronts and backwaters as accessible public edges.

7. Civic Participation and Governance Distance

Across interviews, there is strong civic awareness but limited institutional channels for participation. Citizens express ideas clearly but lack structured mechanisms to influence planning beyond councillor-level engagement.

What this reveals:

- Civic intelligence exists but is underutilised.
- Participation is reactive, not institutionalised.
- Planning is experienced as external rather than collaborative.

Policy direction:

- Establish quarterly open civic forums with published outcomes.
- Create digital + physical participatory platforms at the ward level.
- Integrate citizen feedback into project approval cycles.

Bibliography

Primary Sources (Fieldwork – Interviews)

City Vision Document, Kottayam (2026).

- 29 semi-structured interviews were conducted between 01 February 2026 and 15 March 2026.
- Participants include: senior citizens, youth, teachers, architects, councillors, shop owners, cultural practitioners, and civil society members.
- Interviews anonymised unless otherwise indicated.

Secondary Sources

- Centre for Public Policy Research (CPPR). (2023). Urban planning capacity and workforce analysis in Kerala. Kochi: CPPR.
-
- Government of Kerala. (2023). State Budget Speech 2023–24. Thiruvananthapuram: Finance Department.
-
- Swachh Survekshan. (2023). City cleanliness rankings report. Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, Government of India.
-
- Kerala Kaumudi. (2025). Reporting on municipal waste management practices in Kottayam (Haritha Karma Sena operations and landfill flow issues).
-
- The South First. (2023). Reporting on Kottayam infrastructure delays, including the Central Junction skywalk project status.
-
- World Bank. (2024). Solid waste management support program – Kerala urban municipalities
-
- Malayala Manorama Archives. (selected years). Reporting on Meenachil River pollution, urban flooding, and Kottayam development trends.
-
- Roy, A. (1997). The God of Small Things. IndiaInk.

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Riya is from Kottayam, Kerala and is an architect, designer, illustrator, artist, researcher, and writer with diverse experience in residential design, office spaces, interior renovation, urban planning, and landscape design. Passionate about bringing sociology into design, Riya studies how human behavior shifts through design interventions. She aspires to create architecture that reflects the culture and context of place, valuing the stories behind each building and understanding how design contributes to a location's cultural identity and community well-being.

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Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to ensure small-city voices, often unheard, have the knowledge and tools to influence the development and policies of their communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

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